

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Nurkumalawati, I., & Salsha, N. D. (2023). Evaluation of M-Paspor Application in Indonesia: M-Government Concept Perspective. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 6(4), 241-250.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.06.04.459

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Social and Political Sciences* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Social and Political Sciences, which include, but are not limited to, Anthropology, Government Studies, Political Sciences, Sociology, International Relations, Public Administration, History, Philosophy, Arts, Education, Linguistics, and Cultural Studies. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Social and Political Sciences.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Evaluation of M-Paspor Application in Indonesia: M-Government Concept Perspective

Intan Nurkumalawati¹, Nusyura Divana Salsha²

¹ Immigration Administration Study Program, Immigration Polytechnic, Indonesia

² Bekasi Immigration Office, West Java, Indonesia

Correspondence: Intan Nurkumalawati, Immigration Administration Study Program, Immigration Polytechnic, Indonesia. E-mail: intannurkumalawati@poltekim.ac.id

Abstract

The government utilizes technology to provide internet-based public services, making it easier for the community to access them. One such technology is M-Government, which offers smartphone applications. Immigration Offices in Indonesia have implemented M-Government with the APAPO application. However, there are still several obstacles in its implementation. Applicants experienced difficulties in obtaining a queue number due to the registration quota. Additionally, rescheduling is not possible for those who are unable to attend the office. The Immigration Office conducts biometric records and interviews. To address this issue, the Directorate General of Immigration has introduced a new innovation called Mobile Passport (M-Paspor). The purpose of this study is to evaluate the M-Paspor application based on the M-Government concepts. Qualitative methods were used, with data collected through interviews and observations. The study suggests that the M-Paspor application aligns with the M-Government concept, allowing the public to independently apply for a passport using their smartphone at any time and place. The aim of the M-Paspor application is to simplify the passport application process for the public.

Keywords: M-Government, Mobile Government, M-Paspor

1. Introduction

The use of online information system networks between government agencies is one of the solutions taken by the government in organizing good governance, especially in implementing technology-based services (Nugroho, 2016). One form of technology utilization carried out by the government is mobile government (M-government), which is implemented by using government services and applications that can only be used with mobile phones, laptops or notebooks, and wireless network infrastructure (Handayaningsih & Nugroho, 2013). The utilization of technology is carried out in order to provide internet-based public services to facilitate the community in obtaining public services.

Immigration Offices in Indonesia have implemented M-government in providing immigration services, especially passport processing services for Indonesian Citizens (WNI). Previously there was an application to get a passport queue number known as the Online Passport Application Queue Registration Application (APAPO) based on the Circular of the Director General of Immigration No. IMI-UM.01.01-4166 of 2017 concerning Implementation of the Online Passport Application Queue Registration Application (APAPO). In its implementation, several obstacles are still experienced by the community such as the difficulty of getting a queue number through the APAPO application due to the registration quota which is only opened once a week. In addition, prospective applicants who are unable to attend the Immigration Office to record biometrics and conduct interviews so that the queue number is missed cannot reschedule (Handrisal, Nazaki, & Hafiz, 2021). This condition certainly has an impact on hampering the process of providing immigration services, be it making a new passport or replacing a passport provided by the Immigration Office.

To overcome previous problems, the Directorate General of Immigration implemented a new innovation called Mobile Passport, hereinafter abbreviated as M-Paspor. Unlike the APAPO application, the M-Paspor application has advantages. Quoted from the official website of the Directorate General of Immigration, Ajeng Rahma Saftiri (2021) wrote that the advantages of the M-Paspor application are that passport applicants can apply for a passport and upload scanned requirement files so that they do not need to carry a copy of the file to make it more environmentally friendly because it is non-paper or paperless, there is a feature to reschedule arrival if the queue number is missed or if the prospective applicant is unable to attend on a predetermined day, and a feature to check the status of the passport application.

M-Paspor was first introduced to the public on December 30, 2021 and a trial phase was carried out first at three Immigration Offices, namely the South Jakarta Non-TPI Special Class I Immigration Office, the Central Jakarta Non-TPI Class I Immigration Office, and the Tangerang Non-TPI Class I Immigration Office (Safitri, 2021). The acceleration of the implementation of passport service innovations through the M-Paspor application continues to be improved by the Directorate General of Immigration, so that on February 18, 2022 a letter was issued by the Director of Immigration Traffic number IMI.2-UM.01.01-4.0700 concerning Follow-up Implementation and Policy for Implementing Mobile Passports (M-Paspors) at 107 Immigration Offices.

The Directorate General of Immigration has informed the procedures for using the M-Paspor application ("Procedures for Using M-Paspors," 2022). The step that must be taken by the applicant for the first operation of the M- Passport application is that the applicant is required to download the M-Paspor application on a certain platform according to the device used. Playstore for android users and App Store for IOS users. After successfully downloading the M- Passport application, the applicant registers to get an account by inputting personal data for account registration. After the applicant has an account on the M-Paspor application, the applicant will be directed to log in. If the login is successful, at the time of logging in the application for the first time a terms and conditions page will appear and confirm its approval. After approval, there will be a homepage display of the M- Passport application that displays the passport application menu.

In implementing the M-Paspor application, Immigration Offices is very concerned about the immigration security function. Sub Coordinator of Public Relations of the Directorate General of Immigration Achmad Nur Saleh through Ajeng Rahma Saftitri (2022) said that the applicant still has to bring the original document to check the authenticity and correctness of the data that matches the applicant's personal data. This step is carried out when the applicant comes to the Immigration Office for an interview and biometric recording. This will prevent data falsification, and avoid the practice of PMI-NP (Non-Procedural Indonesian Migrant Workers).

There are several previous studies that are used as references in writing this research. The first research was conducted by Handrisal, Nazaki, and Muhammad Hafiz with the title "Electronic Government-Based Service Innovation through the Online Passport Queue Registration Application (APAPO) at the Class I Immigration Office in Tanjung Pinang in 2019" (Handrisal et al., 2021). The results of the research obtained using the analysis of innovation theory by Rogers found that service innovation using the APAPO application implemented at the Tanjung Pinang Class I Immigration Office was quite successful, although of the four success factors used there were two factors that were still not maximally implemented. The four success factors

used include; innovation characteristics, communication channels, efforts from agents, and social systems. The two factors that have not been fulfilled are communication channels and efforts from agents. The difference in this study lies in the object of research, which previously discussed the APAPO application and this study discusses the M-Paspor application which is an update of the APAPO application.

Another research was conducted by Nurkumalawati and Rofii (2023). The study presents a netnographic review of the adoption of the M-Paspor application from the user's perspective. The review is based on a sample of 1032 comments collected from the Google app review section between February and August 2022. The data was analysed using N-Vivo to explore users' experiences, sentiments, and opinions by examining words, phrases, and sentences related to the use of the M-Paspor app. The difference is that previous research discusses how much influence the implementation of innovations at the Immigration Office has on the community. Based on these problems and phenomena, this study examines how the implementation of the M-Paspor application is based on M- government theory and its suitability for the 4 stages of E-government development. Therefore the objectives of this research are to evaluate the implementation of the M-Paspor Application based on the Mobile Government concept and to examine the concept and stages of development that have been implemented by the M-Paspor application.

2. Mobile Government

Mobile government or M-government is the application of E-government that uses communication media that can move (mobile), for example providing services in the form of government-owned applications on smartphones, laptops and notebooks that are used to provide services to the public (Handayaningsih & Nugroho, 2013). Andhika (2016) explains that the implementation of M-government is a strategy by the government to reduce fraud committed by service providers. This is because the implementation of M-government through smartphones can narrow the space for fraudulent acts committed by officials or officers for personal gain and harm the public including the state because all processes can be monitored directly in the M-government application. It can be concluded that M-government is one form of E-government implementation in the form of government-owned applications contained in smartphones that are used to facilitate the public in obtaining services. The M-Paspor application is a government-owned application that can be downloaded on smartphones created with the aim of providing convenience in the implementation of immigration services in terms of making Indonesian passports.

According to Hong Sheng and Silvana Trimi (2008) the main benefit of implementing M-government is an increase in the coverage of government information and services. M-government allows people to directly access government information and services anytime and anywhere. Meanwhile, Handayaningsih and Nugroho (2013) stated that there are five principles of the benefits of implementing M-government, namely increasing the productivity of employees of public service agencies. This is because M- government allows service officers to add data to the system, thus shortening the time in the data collection process. Second, M-government can increase the effectiveness of the performance of employees of public service agencies. Documents that were originally in physical form, with the use of M- government can be converted in digital form, so employees no longer need to carry documents in paper form. Third, the use of M- government in providing information by the government to the public can be done anytime and anywhere. Fourth, M-government can be used as a means to interact between the community and the government. Fifth, M-government can be used as a means of involving the community to participate in government administration. For example, the government conducts forms of communication with the public such as e-voting, and provides a forum for submitting complaints and testimonials on services provided by the government.

Omar Al-Hujran (2012) suggests factors that influence the successful implementation of M-government services. The first factor is public awareness. This is because the benefits of using electronic-based services such as effectiveness, efficiency, and cost savings cannot be maximally absorbed if people do not use them. The second factor is trust which is an important factor in the implementation of M-government, people are often worried about sharing personal information via the internet due to lack of security, privacy and fear of misuse of personal information. The next factor is the cost factor. The cost in question is the cost that must be incurred to have a

device that can access M- government must be affordable and the costs incurred to access the service must also be reasonable because the high cost of accessing the internet is considered a major obstacle to the implementation of M- government services. The fourth factor is infrastructure constraints, due to frequent problems regarding the non-integration of systems, inadequate bandwidth, and the lack of mobile device capabilities. Another factor is the legal framework, which aims to govern electronic transactions, as well as regulations governing electronic crimes, electronic signatures, and personal data protection.

3. Method

This study conducted with qualitative approach and centered interview to obtain an in-depth description and comprehensive understanding based on the actual situation of the phenomenon to be studied and the researcher acts as a key instrument to obtain the data needed in the research (Yusanto, 2020). This research method was chosen because it can be used to analyze the topic in this study, namely regarding the implementation of the M-Paspor application, then the data and information obtained will be analyzed using the M-government concept. The data sources in this study were obtained by taking field data and data obtained indirectly from pre-existing sources. The field data in question is a record of the results of interviews conducted with sources and the results of field observations. Meanwhile, data obtained indirectly by researchers in the form of books, journals of previous research (Hermawan, 2018).

The data collection techniques in this study are interview, observation, and document studies. The informants in this research are structural officials, employees at the South Jakarta Immigration Office and applicants using the M- Passport application. These informants include the Head of the Travel Document Service and Verification Division, the Head of the Travel Document Service Section, the Head of the Travel Document Verification and Adjudication Section, officers in the Travel Document Service and Verification Division, and 3 passport applicants of M-Paspor application. The data analyzed utilizing narrative data analysis or narrative analysis approach (Webster and Metrova in Zakiah Darmanita and M.Yusri, 2020). This research uses triangulation techniques to test the validity of the data by collecting data through different methods for comparison (Bachri, 2010). The triangulation technique used is triangulation theory. Nancy Carter (2014) argued that theory triangulation uses different theories to analyze and interpret data.

4. Results and Discussion

The existence of the M-Paspor Application is one of the ways carried out by the government through the Immigration Office to accelerate the implementation of digitization of passport services both new passport services and passport replacement for the people of Indonesia. With this M-Paspor Application, the government certainly has the aims and objectives, namely to prepare for changes in the passport service system with the M-Paspor Application in order to smooth the application implementation at Immigration Offices throughout Indonesia. During the M-Paspor trial period in December 2020 based on the Guidelines for the Implementation of Mobile Passport Number IMI.2.UM.01.01-4.0331 (Implementation of Mobile Passport, 2022), the Directorate General of Immigration involved three Immigration Offices, namely the South Jakarta Non TPI Special Class I Immigration Office, the Central Jakarta Non TPI Class I Immigration Office and the Tangerang Non TPI Class I Immigration Office. The informant of the Travel Document Service Section Head said that after holding several meetings by the Directorate General of Immigration which resulted in a guide to the implementation of the M-Paspor application which contains the M-Paspor work system and the SOP for implementing the M-Paspor application. Based on the Guidelines for the Implementation of Mobile Passport Number IMI.2.UM.01.01-4.0331 (Implementation of Mobile Passport, 2022) M-Paspor application has been implemented at one hundred and seven (107) Immigration Offices throughout Indonesia.

Figure 4.1: SOPAP No. IMI-003.GR.01.02 Regarding Passport Issuance through M-Paspor
 Source: Directorate General of Indonesia

From the figure above, The SOPAP explains the flow of services starting with the applicant coming to the Immigration Office in accordance with the location that has been selected and schedule to come to immigration office and bringing the original passport requirements and proof of M-Paspor list, then the data is checked by the customer service officer and the applicant will get a queue number. Furthermore, the applicant will conduct an interview and take biometrics by officers in the Travel Document Field/Section/Subsection. After that, the Head of Division / Head of Section / Head of Travel Document Subsection checks the suitability of data in the Travel Document Issuance System of the Republic of Indonesia (DPRI). If it is appropriate, then the passport number allocation is carried out, checking the suitability of the data attached to the DPRI with the data stored in the application by the Travel Document Field/Section/Subsection officer and ensuring there are no data errors before the passport is printed. The final stage is to print the passport and conduct a passport quality test and laminate the passport.

Although the M-Paspor application can already be run at the Immigration Office, informants also said that the existence of the M-Paspor application is still not perfect because in addition to several advantages there are still some weaknesses. And these obstacles have not yet been resolved. When the applicant registers through the M-Paspor application and is successful, but when it will be served by officers at the Immigration Office, the registration number has not appeared on the officer's computer. In the application, the applicant has been registered, but in the officer's computer the required documents have not appeared. This is not a crucial problem because it can be solved only by re-scanning the files by officers at the Immigration Office. In addition, there were various problems that arose when this application was first launched, such as applicants who uploaded the wrong documents, applicants made two payments at the time of payment, then after making the payment the proof of payment did not appear.

With the M-Paspor application, application registration is carried out in a timely manner online and later factual verification (data and files) is still mandatory. Through M-Paspor, applicants can apply for a passport by uploading files to the application. So that when coming to the Immigration Office, the applicant only needs to show the original file during the interview stage, thus cutting down on face-to-face time. The superior features of M-Paspor include PNPB payment in advance, passport application status check, validation of Dukcapil NIK, reschedule arrival schedule and integration of Travel Documents of the Republic of Indonesia. Payment is made before the interview at the Immigration Office. Can be done through Banks, marketplaces such as Tokopedia and Bukalapak, Post Offices and Indomaret. The payment deadline is two hours after the document is uploaded, said the Head of Travel Document Services Section. This is certainly different from the Online Passport Queue Registration Application (APAPO), explained by the Head of the Travel Document Services Section that the Registration Application through the APAPO application is an application developed by the Directorate General of Immigration to facilitate the public in processing passports with time-based queues. By using APAPO,

applicants only need to come according to the specified hours and dates. So it cannot be like the M-Paspor application which can upload files to the application and also does not have superior features such as M-Paspor.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by the author to structural officials in the Field of Services and Verification of Travel Documents at the South Jakarta Immigration Office, there are differences that occur in conducting passport services after the implementation of the M-Paspor application. This was conveyed by the Head of the Travel Document Service and Verification Division. He said that there was a considerable difference after using the M-Paspor application in providing passport services to the public, where the applicant had made a payment in advance before coming to the Immigration Office. The applicant is given two hours to complete the payment and if it exceeds this time then the applicant must re-register. In addition, the public also uploads the required documents independently in the M-Paspor application where in the previous application, namely the APAPO application, it was the officer who scanned the required document files at the Immigration Office. With these changes, he said that the implementation of the M-Paspor application has a positive impact on providing services to the community because the services provided no longer require a longer time because the document upload process has been carried out so that when at the Immigration Office only continues the verification and interview process, provided that the uploaded documents are in accordance with the provisions.

Furthermore, according to the Section Head of Travel Document Verification and Adjudication, the M-Paspor Application is a new form of the Online Passport Queue Registration Application (APAPO) which is implemented to make passport services more transparent, accountable and fast. Where there are differences that occur, namely the applicant fills in personal data according to the passport application requirements independently where the data is integrated with the officer's computer at the Immigration Office. He also believes that this change is a very positive change because it shortens the process of stages when providing services at the Immigration Office so that the service process becomes faster. And further said that the target of this M-Paspor application is that it can be accessed by people throughout Indonesia.

According to the Head of the Travel Document Services Section, the main difference is seen when the process of uploading the required document files is carried out at the beginning and PNPB payment for passport services is also made before the applicant comes to the Immigration Office. Meanwhile, when still using the APAPO, the documents were uploaded at the Immigration Office, and payment was made after the verification and interview stages at the Immigration Office. Evidently, M-Paspors are more practical and easier, this will certainly make employee productivity increase in providing services to the community, especially in terms of passport services, this is because with M-Paspors uploading documents and payments have been made in advance, so that the productivity of employees can be further increased by working on other tasks related in passport issuance. This condition is also justified by officers in the Travel Document Service and Verification Division. The results of interviews with applicants also said that using M-Paspors was easier than the previous system with a record of the network being in smooth condition.

With document uploads carried out independently by the applicant and officers no longer scanning documents, the time required by officers in providing services is reduced, which of course makes the productivity of officers will increase. With the faster the service process provided; the more applicants can be served. This is reinforced by a statement from the Head of the Travel Document Service and Verification Division who said that ideally officer productivity increases with the process of uploading required documents independently from the applicant, but provided that the applicant in doing so the uploaded documents is in accordance with the requirements or are not wrong. This will make the time efficiency and work efficiency of Immigration officers.

However, the facts in the field show that there are still issues of applicants uploading documents incorrectly, for example, they should upload a photo of the applicant's family card instead of uploading a family photo, regardless of intentional or unintentional factors. Another fact is that when the applicant has come to the office and has also uploaded documents, but during the interview stage the officer finds suspicions or signs of misuse of the passport application, this makes the officers need more time for verification and the officer gives the applicant about 5 (five) working days to complete the additional documents that are suspended. In addition to these obstacles, there are other obstacles such as those experienced by applicants who carry out the passport

registration process through the M-Paspor application. The obstacle experienced by the applicant is that when making a payment there is a failure and then it has been tried repeatedly but still fails and it even takes up to 1 (one) week for the applicant to successfully make a payment. He said he had tried to come directly to the office to register manually, but the officer refused and still suggested registering through the M-Paspor application. Thus, the applicant continues to wait until it is successful, as previously said, it almost took 1 (one) week to make a successful payment.

Regarding the advantages of the M-Paspor application as said by the Head of the Travel Document Service and Verification Division who stated that with the existence of this M-Paspor, the positive side will cause the community not to take a long time to be served by officers because they have registered independently and have carried out the document upload process independently, so that the Immigration Office only conducts verification and interview stages. Of course, this will not require a long time with a note that the uploaded documents have been in accordance with the necessary requirements and there were no interview results that led to misuse of passport applications. Thus, it can be said that the existence of this M- Passport application has a positive impact. The use of M-Paspors makes work easier, more practical and faster. But behind it is also inseparable from the obstacles in its implementation. In the operation of the M-Paspor in its journey it also encounters certain technical obstacles. Regarding the obstacles in the operation of this system, the Section Head of Travel Document Services said that in overcoming these technical obstacles with the Help Desk counter facility in the implementation of services with the M-Paspor application. If there are obstacles, they will be directed to the M-Paspor Help Desk service, which will be followed up by officers from the Directorate General of Immigration Systems and Technology who will solve the problem, so that officers at the Immigration Office only need to report the help desk ticket to the M-Paspor WhatsApp group as written in Letter Number IMI.2-UM.01.01-4.1996 regarding Follow- up on Implementation and Policy of Mobile Passport (M-Paspor) at the Immigration Office (Implementation of Mobile Passport, 2022). This is done in order to serve responses to problems in M-Paspor services can be served quickly because the officers are always ready to respond during working hours, so they do not have to wait long or even protracted due to problems in the operation.

The use of this Help Desk is also suggested to a named applicant who will register his wife in making a passport, previously the applicant was worried as experienced who made the M-Paspor registration failed and only succeeded in approximately one week due to system problems. Regarding the use of this M-Paspor, the applicant said that getting information about the M-Paspor application is very easy because it is found in various sources, so there is no difficulty in obtaining such information. The applicant further said that he felt easier with the application before the M-Paspor, he said that only by registering once it was immediately processed and the passport making process went smoothly, but with this M- Passport he said he had to register repeatedly, so he felt easier with the previous application, namely APAPO compared to M-Paspor. According to the Head of the Travel Document Service and Verification Division, technical obstacles are still found, including some applicant data that is not included in the computer or the Republic of Indonesia Travel Document Issuance System Application. This is indicated by the applicant in the application on his smart phone to the officer that he has registered but apparently the application data from the applicant has not entered the officer's computer. In connection with this, the officer is forced to re-scan and the applicant is still served as long as he can show proof on the applicant's smartphone and proof of payment. Like the obstacles experienced by one of the applicants where when registering online through M- Passport and getting network constraints are not smooth or are maintenance or maintenance. With these conditions, some applicant decided to come directly to the Immigration Office to register again with the assistance of an officer, where at the time it was explained that there was an error in the optional selection of an electronic passport which made the applicant fail in registration. Then with the help of the officer finally succeeded in registering, but that was not the only obstacle experienced by the applicant, when going to make a payment it also had to take a very long time even though in the end the payment could be made.

Other impediments were also found in other applicants who said that registering through M-Paspor failed and it took two days before it was successful. Some applicant said that it was better to register manually by coming to the Immigration Office, where at that time registration was carried out using the website, after which an interview was conducted and biometric records were recorded then waited for the passport printing process and

passport collection. Another applicant said that registration before M-Paspor was easier, using M-Paspor made it difficult and took longer according to him. The obstacles experienced the applicant are in the form of requiring a long time until they can upload the required documents, then when making payments they also have to wait a long time for the payment billing code and the code can only be used within a span of two to three hours. Thus, in using this M-Paspor application according to the applicant, it takes up quite a lot of time.

In addition to the obstacles in the operation of M-Paspor, it turns out that this application also still has some shortcomings in passport making services for people who want to make arrangements. As said by the Section Head of Travel Document Services that although the M-Paspor Application has several advantages, it also has weaknesses. These weaknesses include not accommodating applicants with damaged or lost passports or in essence those who need BAP have not been accommodated. In this case M-Paspor is only limited to making new passports and replacements without any obstacles and without any suspicion from officers during interviews. In terms of transparency and control, the use of M-Paspor is not much different from the previous application, namely APAPO, because in both applications, both APAPO and M-Paspor in terms of PNBK payments have gone directly to the State treasury through the bank so that it is no longer through the PNBK. So that in terms of transparency and control it is the same or there has not been a significant increase in the use of the M-Paspor application. Furthermore, according to the informant of the Head of the Travel Document Service and Verification Division, through the M-Paspor application, there is an increase in transparency and supervision carried out to the officers. Because, the applicant has registered independently and the applicant can also choose the Immigration Office freely in making a passport and the applicant can also choose the time-of-service hours. In addition to increased productivity, the M-Paspor application is also more transparent in the implementation of passport services when compared to passport services when the M-Paspor application has not been implemented. This is shown in the M-Paspor application written what documents are needed and the requirements and under certain conditions have been explained in detail in the M-Paspor application, including rescheduling, canceling, and if it does not meet certain requirements and certain returns are all listed.

The application of the M-Paspor in providing services to the public, Immigration Offices is based on the principle of the benefits of implementing M-Government according to Handayaningsih and Nugroho (2013). The benefits are the integration of applicant data that has been uploaded to the M-Paspor application with the Republic of Indonesia Travel Document Issuance System at the Immigration Office so as to shorten the time in the data collection process. Second, there is an increase in the effectiveness of employee performance in providing services to the community because officers no longer need to scan applicant documents. Third, the M-Paspor application can be accessed at any time not tied to the working hours of the Immigration Office and can be accessed anywhere by the public. However, there are two principles of benefits that have not been fulfilled in the application of the M- Passport. Firstly, it has not provided interactive services that allow the community to interact with the Immigration Office. Secondly, there is no room or a forum for submitting complaints and testimonials on the services provided in the M-Paspor application in the context of implementing community participation in governance.

Based on the factors that influence the successful implementation of M- Government services proposed by Omar Al-Hujran (2012), the first is the use of M-Government services by the community. The public knows and uses the M-Paspor application. With the use of the M-Paspor application by the community, the benefits of using electronic-based services such as cutting the service time for passport applications can be felt. The second factor is trust, that people strongly believe in sharing personal data in this case uploading Identity Cards (KTP), Family Cards (KK), and other personal data in the M-Paspor application. The third factor is the cost factor, namely the costs incurred to access M- Government services. Today, many people are already using smartphones with internet facilities that make it possible to access the M-Paspor application. The fourth factor is infrastructure constraints, which have been mentioned that there are still frequent system problems such as the non-integration of applicant data in the M-Paspor application and data on the Republic of Indonesia Travel Document Issuance System.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion, it can be concluded that the implementation of the M-Paspor Application in Immigration Office made passport issuance process more effective than before. Problems that arise can also be overcome, such as if the applicant's data does not appear in the SPRI system even though they have uploaded documents in the M-Paspor application, the files will be rescanned at the interview and biometric counters. M-Paspor is in accordance with the concept of M-government that people can apply for passports independently using their smartphones which can be done anytime and anywhere, so that the purpose and objectives of the M-Paspor application make it easier for people to apply for passports. However, there are two principles that have not been fulfilled in the application of the M- Passport: it has not provided interactive services that allow the community to interact with the Immigration Office and there is no room for submitting complaints and testimonials.

There are several suggestions that can be conveyed based on the findings in this study: improving the infrastructure of the M-Paspor system considering that there are still frequent errors in the M-Paspor application. This must be followed up immediately considering that the repair is central and centralized through the Directorate General of Immigration. In addition, the Directorate General of Immigration can start providing interactive services on the M-Paspor application which aims to make it easier for the public to interact to submit questions, complaints, or suggestions for the services provided. In addition to make it easier for the public to obtain information, this can also help the Immigration Office in analyzing problems that are often encountered by the public in using the M-Paspor application so that it can be used as evaluation material and resolved immediately.

Author Contributions: All authors contributed to this research

Funding: NA

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics approval: Not applicable.

References:

- Al-Hujran, O. (2012). Toward the Utilization of M-Government Services in Developing Countries: A Qualitative Investigation. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(5), 155-160. Retrieved from http://www.ijbssnet.com/journals/Vol_3_No_5_March_2012/17.pdf
- Andhika, L. R. (2016). Mobile Government as Early Prevention on Performance Deviations of State Civil Apparatus Mobile Government as Early Prevention on Performance. *Civil Service*, 10(2), 29-42.
- Bachri, B. S. (2010). Ensuring Data Validity Through Triangulation in Qualitative Research.
- Carter, N. (2014). The Use of Triangulation in Qualitative Research. 41(5). Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/docview/1559261620>
- Darmanita, Z., & Yusri, M. (2020). Operation of Narrative and Ethnographic Research; Definition, Principles, Procedures, Analysis, Interpretation and Reporting of findings. 1(1994).
- Handayaningsih, S., & Nugroho, H. (2013). M-Government System Model (Case Study: Yogyakarta City Government). *Ahmad Dahlan University Yogyakarta, Informatics Engineering Study Program*, 7(2), 814-815.
- Handrisal, H., Nazaki, N., & Hafiz, M. (2021). Electronic Government-Based Service Innovation Through the Online Passport Queue Registration Application (Apapo) at the Tanjungpinang Class I Immigration Office in 2019. *KEMUDI: Journal of Government Science*, 5(02), 179-198. <https://doi.org/10.31629/kemudi.v5i02.3104>
- Hermawan, H. (2018). Qualitative Methods for Tourism Research. *Journal of Communication*, p. 20.
- Implementation of Mobile Passport. (2022). Performance Report of the Directorate General of Immigration of the Ministry of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia 2021.

- Indrajit, R. E. (2016). Electronic government. Concepts and Strategies of Electronic Government, 86. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03251472>
- Lusiani, C., & Nugroho, L. E. (2008). Evaluating the Effectiveness of Electronic Services in the Public Sector: Case Study of Mobile Government Services in Sleman Regency Government. 2008.
- M-Paspor Implementation Procedure. (2022). Retrieved from <https://kanibatam.kemenkumham.go.id/page/tata-cara-penggunaan-m- passport>
- Nugroho, T. (2016). Analysis of E-government to Public Services in the Ministry of Law and Human Rights. *Scientific Journal of Legal Policy*, 10(3), 279-296.
- Nurkumalawati, I., & Rofii, M. S. (2023). Public Review of M-Paspor Application in Indonesia: Mobile Government, Digital Resilience, Cyber Security. Proceedings of the Fifth Annual International Conference on Business and Public Administration (AICoBPA 2022). Atlantis Press. doi:10.2991/978-2-38476-090-9_32
- Safitri, A. R. (2021). Immigration Introduces M-Paspor Application. Retrieved from <https://www.imigrasi.go.id/en/2021/12/30/imigrasi-perkenalkan-aplikasi-m- passport/>
- Safitri, A. R. (2022). How to Use M-Paspor. (January 19). Retrieved from <https://www.imigrasi.go.id/en/2022/01/19/cara-menggunakan-m-paspor-dari- beginning-to-end-easy-and-fast/>
- Samsara, L. (2013). Passport Service Innovation at the Immigration Office (Study on Improving the Quality of Travel Document Services of the Republic of Indonesia at the Surabaya Special Class I Immigration Office). *Journal of Public Policy and Management*, 1(1), 6-15. Retrieved from <http://journal.unair.ac.id/download- fullpapers-Ladiatno Samsara.pdf>
- Sheng, H., & Trimi, S. (2008). M-government: Technologies, applications and challenges. *Electronic Government*, 5(1), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1504/EG.2008.016124>
- Widodo, N. (2016). Development of e-Government in Local Government in order to Realize Smart City (Study in Malang City Local Government). *Scientific Journal of Public Administration*, 2(4), 227-235. <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.jiap.2016.002.04.15>
- Yusanto, Y. (2020). Variety of Qualitative Research Approaches. *Journal of Scientific Communication (Jsc)*, 1(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.31506/jsc.v1i1.7764>